

Manuscript Details

Manuscript number	FORPOL_2018_382_R1
Title	Can social innovation make a difference to forest-dependent communities?
Article type	Research Paper

Abstract

Attention to social innovation and its role in sustainable development have been rising. However, the knowledge of social innovation pertaining to rural areas, including the forestry sector is lacking. Therefore, in this Special Issue of Forest Policy and Economics we exchange understandings and advance scientific knowledge of the role and place of social innovation in the development of forest-dependent communities and of forest social-ecological systems, underpinning this development. Papers included in this Issue blend diverse theoretical positions into a coherent explanation of spatial variability, case and context specificity of social innovation, encompassing its empirical diversity, complexities and multiple dimensions. The suggested articles improve existing knowledge of determinants of success seeking to answer the question of how to support enhanced governance and social innovations, addressing multiplicity and priorities of social needs, and new social relationships and collaborations. We also provide innovative solutions and sustainable forestry considerations, ideas potentially useful for policy makers and practice communities of different levels, having ultimate aims of increasing the well-being of forest-dependent communities and building the resilience to changes taking place in remote rural areas of Europe and beyond.

Keywords social innovation, forestry, communities, marginal rural areas

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The final published version is available direct from the publisher website at:
[10.1016/j.forpol.2019.01.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2019.01.001)

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4 **Can social innovation make a difference to forest-dependent communities?**
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1 **Abstract**

2 Attention to social innovation and its role in sustainable development have been rising.
3 However, the knowledge of social innovation pertaining to rural areas, including the forestry
4 sector is lacking. Therefore, in this Special Issue of Forest Policy and Economics we exchange
5 understandings and advance scientific knowledge of the role and place of social innovation in
6 the development of forest-dependent communities and of forest social-ecological systems,
7 underpinning this development. Papers included in this Issue blend diverse theoretical positions
8 into a coherent explanation of spatial variability, case and context specificity of social
9 innovation, encompassing its empirical diversity, complexities and multiple dimensions. The
10 suggested articles improve existing knowledge of determinants of success seeking to answer
11 the question of how to support enhanced governance and social innovations, addressing
12 multiplicity and priorities of social needs, and new social relationships and collaborations. We
13 also provide innovative solutions and sustainable forestry considerations, ideas potentially
14 useful for policy makers and practice communities of different levels, having ultimate aims
15 of increasing the well-being of forest-dependent communities and building the resilience to
16 changes taking place in remote rural areas of Europe and beyond.

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Can social innovation make a difference to forest-dependent communities?

1. Introduction

Forests provide timber, food, fuel and non-wood forest products, and have important ecological functions, such as carbon storage, nutrient cycling, water and air purification, and the maintenance of wildlife habitat. The social and cultural benefits of forests are associated with recreation, education, and the hosting of sites of high spiritual value. Forests are of particular significance to communities living in marginalized rural areas, where people have difficulties in common regarding biophysical factors, transport and digital infrastructure, housing, and ageing populations. These are compounded by global pressures of climate change, and challenges of addressing energy and food security.

All these challenges, particularly facing forest-dependent communities, require urgent solutions. Increasingly, social innovation is being viewed as a promising means of responding to social demands (BEPA, 2011). There has been an accompanying increase in the need to understand social innovation and its role in attaining a more sustainable use of forest ecosystem services for the benefit of communities, including those who are forest-dependent (Polman et al., 2017; Kluvankova et al., 2018, This Issue).

The project ‘Social Innovation in Marginalised¹ Rural Areas’ (SIMRA, 2016-2020), funded by the European Union’s (EU) Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (www.simra-h2020.eu), is developing an improved understanding of social innovation and how it can be used to enhance societal well-being in marginalized rural areas. This Special Issue of Forest

¹ For more information on the term marginalised rural areas and its explanation see Price et al., 2017.

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62 Policy and Economics, as a product of the SIMRA project and our Thematic Session
63 197 organised at the 125th Anniversary IUFRO Congress (<http://iufro2017.com/>), is a
64 contribution to advancing and exchanging scientific knowledge of social innovation in the
65 context of forestry (IUFRO, 2018). A purpose of This Issue is also to promote social learning;
66 contribute ideas on social innovation that are potentially helpful for the development of rural
67 policy and sustainable forestry, and ideas useful for practice communities at various levels. The
68 ultimate aim of this work is to increase the well-being of forest-dependent communities and
69 assist them in building resilience to challenges currently faced.
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81 We believe that it is timely and worthy for scientists, the community of practice and local
82 people living in marginalized rural areas, to explore the concept of social innovation and its
83 implementation, to share ideas on theory, models and their applicability, as well as on the
84 evaluation of outcomes and impacts of social innovation on the ground.
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92 **2. Understanding and Advancing Social Innovation**

93 Innovation, including social innovation, is considered a driving force of sustainable
94 development. It helps regenerate the local economy and/or improve people's quality of life.
95 Social innovation has been central to improvements in health care, education, transportation,
96 green space, etc. (Ezell and Atkinson, 2010). The ideas around social innovation build upon
97 the research and networks developed by the European Commission and social and
98 interdisciplinary scientists (European Council, 2013; Hubert, 2011; Caulier-Grice et al., 2010;
99 Hubert, 2011; Bock, 2016). These ideas are adding value to the knowledge of social innovation
100 and strengthen its links with policy and practice. The following conceptual elements (SIMRA,
101 2016) are considered particularly relevant for developing the theoretical underpinning of social
102 innovation and important for us in the context of forestry.
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121 The origins of (entrepreneurial) *innovation theory* are associated with Schumpeter (1932). Ray
122 (2002) observed neo-endogenous development within a territorial context and through new
123 institutional forms involving social innovations. In a rural context, ideas about endogenous and
124 neo-endogenous development have been promoted (Van Der Ploeg and Long, 1994). Other
125 authors (e.g. Nardone et al., 2010) have investigated typologies of social innovation and its
126 'diffusion' mechanisms. How innovations diffuse amongst actors has been explored (Floridi et
127 al., 2012; Rogers, 2003). *Social enterprise learning* has emerged in the context of rural
128 regeneration. Heterogeneities in social learning were recognized as important to explain
129 patterns of adoption and diffusion of social innovation, and potentially to reduce the market
130 failures of meeting social needs (Wolf and Zilberman, 2001).
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145 The concepts of human capital and trust attracted attention (La Porta, et al., 1997; Valve, 2006;
146 BEPA, 2010; Sauer and Zilberman, 2012), with trust between key policy actors being
147 considered as a precondition for success (Fukuyama, 1995). As the theoretical work began to
148 recognize the critical role of *social capital* (Coleman, 1988; Putnam, 1993; Lehtonen, 2004),
149 the focus has shifted towards analyzing *institutions and interactions* between stakeholders.
150 Hybrid institutional forms, e.g. partnerships and coalitions, have become central (Defourny and
151 Nyssens, 2008).
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162 Social innovation re-emerged as a concept and practice to address economic restructuring and
163 increased social needs. The innovation systems approach has spread (Enkvist et al., 2007;
164 Albert and Laberge, 2007). Ideas around regional innovation systems (Cooke, 2001), territorial
165 capital (OECD, 2000; Camagni and Capello, 2010) and the innovative milieu (Camagni, 1991)
166 have come closer in their understanding of the role of social relationships and other institutional
167 factors in realizing of development outcomes.
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180 The concept of institutions (setting the ‘rules of the game’, c.f. Ostrom, 2009) have become
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182 recognized as the constraints that shape human interactions (Young, 2002). The idea of an
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184 institutional transformation in forestry was proposed (Vatn, 2005; Nijnik and Oskam, 2004;
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186 Primmer et al., 2014; Buttoud et al., 2011), along with the notion of *transitions* (Rotmans and
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188 Loorbach, 2009; Nijnik and Mather, 2006). The concept of ‘social innovation parks’ has
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190 emerged (Lundström and Zhou, 2011), developing into the idea of social innovation incubators,
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192 and accompanied by a disruptive-innovation model of ‘catalytic innovations’ (Christensen,
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194 2008). The concept of transitions has started addressing societal change by offering solutions
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196 aimed at disadvantaged groups and regions, ensuring that social innovations are practical,
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198 including in marginalized areas and forest-dependent communities (SIMRA, 2016).
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203 We argue that no one theoretical position can explain phenomena as diverse in nature, context
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205 and scale as social innovation (SIMRA, 2016). However, Mulgan (2006; 2010) ‘connected
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207 difference’ theory presents an eclectic synthesis of relevant theories and empirical observations
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209 of social innovation which are developed around practice. The conceptualisation of social
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211 innovation by SIMRA is presented in Kluvankova et al. (2018, This Issue) and Polman et al.
212
213 (2017). This conceptualization draws on the theories and connects to its implementation in an
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215 open society (‘new economics’, BEPA, 2011). The guiding definition of social innovation used
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217 by us is that it is “the reconfiguring of social practices, in response to societal challenges, which
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219 seeks to enhance outcomes on societal well-being and necessarily includes the engagement of
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221 civil society actors (Polman et al., 2017).”
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227 In this Special Issue, we share with readers: i) a body of conceptually coherent knowledge as
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229 a platform for examining social innovation in forest-dependent communities; ii) enhanced
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231 means for assessing the nature and effectiveness of social innovation; and iii) findings from
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239 empirical research to observe, evaluate and promote social innovation in marginalized rural
240 areas and communities. The findings included in This Issue build on an extensive pool of
241 knowledge accumulated from different theoretical perspectives of social innovation,
242 recognizing that much of the previous work has related to city regions and regional social
243 innovation systems. We argue that most innovation theories have not been rural areas-specific,
244 forestry-specific, or specifically addressing forest-dependent communities. Thus, the articles
245 in This Issue tend to fill this knowledge gap.
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257 A variety of approaches are adopted to study social innovation in forest-dependent
258 communities and its specificities arising in different settings. This Issue provides readers with
259 examples of social innovation in forest-dependent communities that are associated with
260 distinctive demographic characteristics from various regions of Europe and beyond, with issues
261 of social cohesion, place-specific (endogenous) knowledge, institutional weakness and above-
262 average economic decline. The articles imply that social innovation can bring new solutions to
263 problems in marginalised rural areas that are facing challenges partly posed by their
264 transformations into an increasingly global and knowledge-based economy (Nyseth and
265 Aarsæther, 2005). In this context, marginalized areas are re-inventing their role, and forest-
266 dependent communities are developing their capacity to innovate.
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280 Still, a ‘social innovation implementation deficit’ is noted in some of these areas (Knill and
281 Lenschow, 2000). Much remains to be done to link social innovations with desired policy
282 outcomes (Koontz and Thomas, 2006). Social innovations require to be considered through the
283 entire cycle (The Young Foundation, 2012) of the spiral model: from *ideas, to prototyping and*
284 *piloting, to implementation, and upscaling*. It is the cycle from ideas to production and markets
285 (e.g. new entrepreneur opportunities), and towards innovative policy and governance
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mechanisms within each scale and across the scales (c.f. Weiss et al., 2011). This implies that attention has been given to new social networks and partnerships, horizontal and vertical networks, specifically those involving forest-dependent communities.

Trans-disciplinary science is well placed to address the complexity and causalities of social innovations. It can link abstract knowledge (through social innovation processes towards experience-based competencies and skills, Polman et al., 2014) to target knowledge (which is a set of social innovation outputs), to create impacts in marginalized rural areas and communities (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Systems model of knowledge flow (SIMRA, 2016)

Importantly, the science around social innovations develops through the interactions of participating experts: scientists of relevant disciplines, policy-makers and practitioners (entrepreneurs, knowledge brokers and innovators), facilitated by their partnerships. Its outputs will then be both scientific and practical, including transferable methods, tools, models, strategies and participatory processes to enhance social innovation.

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357 Research findings presented in the Special Issue focus on these topics (Secco et al., 2018 This
358 Issue; Kluvankova et al., 2018, This Issue). They also provide evidence that local forest-
359 dependent communities and other relevant actors can improve the delivery of sustainable, smart
360 and socially innovative solutions in marginalized rural areas (Khadka et al., 2018, This Issue).
361 This is achieved through the development of appropriate policy instruments (e.g. governance
362 mechanisms, incentives) and interventions (e.g. training, learning, trust-building, facilitation
363 of innovative cultures) (Ludvig et al., 2018a, This Issue).
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374 The studies reported in This Issue consider the development of social innovation capacity,
375 related to products and partnerships, from ideas to implementation. The importance is shown
376 of connecting top-down stimulating policy with bottom-up endogenous action and the need to
377 ‘get this right’. Several papers in the Issue use case studies as a platform across a range of
378 contexts to identify the framework conditions under which social innovation can make a
379 difference across the forest-dependent communities. They stress the importance of funding
380 throughout all stages of the innovation life-cycle, social innovation incubators (to enable
381 experiments) and networks, social learning and capacity building as enabling factors for the
382 promotion of social innovation on the ground.
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393 394 395 **3. Papers of the Special Issue** 396

397 The papers in this Special Issue focus on identifying and explaining the role and place of social
398 innovation, and the enabling policies and decision-making processes, which lead to an increase
399 in the sustainability and multi-functionality of forests to the benefit of the communities which
400 depend upon them. A substantial knowledge gap exists in the understanding and development
401 of social innovation in marginalised rural areas. This gap was particularly notable in relation
402 to forestry, for which there was limited empirical evidence of social innovation or innovative
403 governance, and the supporting conditions required for either (SIMRA, 2016). This Special
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416 Issue was designed to fill the knowledge gap, and to advance and share understanding of social
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418 innovation in forest dependent communities in marginalized rural areas.
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423 The Special Issue brings together evidence to suggest that social innovations (SIMRA, 2016)
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425 and social-ecological innovations (Melnykovich et al., 2018) can be a means of creating
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427 opportunities for forest-dependent areas and their communities to overcome contemporary
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429 challenges and advance their sustainability. The evidence from the papers shows that joint
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431 societal initiatives and innovative actions can help the development of capabilities to tackle the
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433 challenges that remote rural areas currently face. Such joint working involves scientific and
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435 practice stakeholders, policy and third-sector actors and representatives of local, forest-
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437 dependent communities, along with a suitable combination of top-down and bottom up
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439 governance approaches, supported by appropriate policy instruments and incentives.
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444 Kluvankova et al. (2018, This Issue) define ‘forest-dependent communities’ as being located
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446 in marginalized rural areas, and closely connected to the ecosystem services supplied by
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448 forests. The well-being of such communities (in its wider sense) is directly and positively
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450 dependent on the sustainability of forests and the forestry sector. Drawing on theoretical
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452 positions, Kluvankova et al. (2018, This Issue) provide the SIMRA definition of social
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454 innovation for marginalised rural areas and identify the types of social innovation most likely
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456 to be adopted by forest-dependent communities.
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461 The authors characterize the emergence of social innovations as a collective action, which is
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463 nurtured or constrained by the socio-economic (including institutional) and environmental
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465 contexts that frame the dynamics of changes. The authors identify key mechanisms that enable
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467 social innovations to emerge and to develop. A framework is proposed for understanding the
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475 relationships, factors and path dependencies of social innovations, and applied in relation to
476 forest-dependent communities.
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482 The EU is increasingly embracing social innovation as a means of addressing societal
483 challenges, such as the delocalization of industry, decline in some economic activities,
484 population ageing, migration, poverty, and for rebuilding community resilience (European
485 Council, 2013). However, it is not clear how to evaluate the processes of social innovation and
486 its impacts (e.g. enhanced human wellbeing), resulting in no agreed methodologies for such
487 evaluations.
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497 Secco et al. (2018, This Issue) provide a science-stakeholder co-constructed analysis of which
498 aspects of social innovation should be evaluated, and which characteristics of an evaluation
499 method would be most appropriate for capturing such aspects. They illustrate the requirement
500 for primary data relating to community-based local initiatives, and the benefits of using
501 qualitative and quantitative methods and indicators, together with a combination of expert and
502 participatory-based evaluation approaches, to capture innovative processes.
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511 Several papers in the Special Issue address community and policy implications of social
512 innovation (Ludvig et al., 2018, This Issue). Public policy provides an important driver of
513 change in rural areas, acting across scales: from global to local. Policy measures and associated
514 processes can have a decisive impact on forest-dependent communities. Key policy-driven
515 outcomes include land use changes, the development of infrastructure, recreation activities,
516 transitions to low carbon energy systems and community based renewable energy projects
517 (Harnmeijer et al., 2018). However, such changes can have negative impacts.
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534 In some places, the policy drivers can lead to the intensification of land use practices,
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536 observable through their impacts on cultural landscapes, or lead to land abandonment, often
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538 followed by forest regeneration. The timing and pace of changes happening simultaneously can
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540 create ecological and social challenges. Multiple and diverse changes and challenges currently
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542 faced by forest-dependent communities require effective policy decisions at a local level, as
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544 well as the implementation of participatory governance and ecosystem-based management
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546 practices (Nijnik et al., 2017; Sarkki et al., 2017).
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551 Ludvig et al. (2018b, This Issue) focus on the policies that offer potential to support social
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553 innovation in remote and vulnerable rural areas. They report that many such policies have little
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555 in common in terms of their individual targets. The article outlines a categorization of the
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557 policies that have some form of link with social innovation by targeting major societal
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559 challenges, vulnerable social groups, and policies targeting the participatory inclusion of civil
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561 society in decision-making. In addition, they outline policy factors that foster or hinder social
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563 innovation in rural areas.
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568 The challenges of governance are of considerable importance for forest-dependent
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570 communities. Common challenges include the lack of transparency and difficulties in
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572 balancing top-down and bottom-up decision-making mechanisms, asymmetric information and
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574 problems with knowledge exchange, as well as a deficiency of stakeholder participation in
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576 decision-making processes (Nijnik et al., 2018, This Issue). It is shown that a cohesive policy
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578 which combines top-down and bottom-up approaches, including local initiatives and social
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580 innovations, could be a solution to tackling challenges faced by marginalised rural areas.
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593 The creation of new institutions and/or governance arrangements which help forest-dependent
594 communities tackle global challenges, would also contribute to delivering the UN Sustainable
595 Development Goals 2030 Agenda. The sustainable use of forest ecosystem services provides a
596 significant contribution to the well-being of forest-dependent communities by building
597 resilience and developing new social arrangements or networks between actors. In
598 marginalized rural areas, where people face particular types of disadvantages (Price et al.,
599 2017), social innovation offers solutions that create and implement new ideas which have the
600 potential to deliver value.
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612 Sarkki et al. (This Issue) studied the role of human values in social innovations in four forest-
613 dependent communities in Europe. Relational values, which are derivative of the relationships
614 between human and non-human world, and responsibilities towards these relationships, were
615 divided into three categories: Doing, Belonging and Respecting. The authors examined
616 practical, institutional and normative dimensions of social innovation that sustain these values.
617 Their findings suggest that relational values, represented by the concepts of Doing, Belonging
618 and Respecting, may be constructive only, if/when basic material needs, and ‘Instrumental’
619 values of forest-dependent people are satisfied. Common components of social innovation are
620 shown to be strong relationships between people, people and nature, and new or re-established
621 co-management arrangements based on empowered individuals, communities or institutions.
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637 Social innovation also entails the development of new practices which target new products,
638 services, models and new social relationships, and collaborations, as well as new fields of
639 activity, e.g. social entrepreneurship and social enterprises (SIMRA, 2016). Empirical evidence
640 of these characteristics of social innovation, reported in this Special Issue, include examples of
641 community-owned renewable energy initiatives (Soloviy et al., This Issue), and co-operatives
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652 for the development of local traditional products in the Ukrainian Carpathians, where local
653 farmers have created an association for local sheep cheese production, along with ecotourism
654 and the promotion of facets of local culture.
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661 Sarkki et al. (This Issue) propose a framework for examining social innovations, drawing on
662 findings from case studies in Ukraine, Finland, Slovenia and the UK (Scotland). Other papers
663 in this Special Issue examine institutional and practical implications of social innovation in the
664 contexts of their countries and settings. These include treeline areas of the Carpathians (Nijnik
665 et al., 2018, This Issue), Mediterranean forests (Gorriz-Mifsud et al., This Issue), and
666 woodlands in Slovenia (Rogelja et al., 2018, This Issue), Switzerland (Wilkes-Allemand and
667 Ludvig, 2018, This Issue), and the UK (Wales) (Ludvig et al., 2018b, This Issue).
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678 The authors of these papers contribute to the literature on social innovation with empirical
679 evidence and insights into success factors of social innovations in forestry settings. They
680 suggest approaches for the co-production of innovative knowledge and the promotion of
681 bottom-up stakeholder engagement processes to enhance community resilience and improve
682 the sustainability of socio-ecological systems (Sarkki et al., This Issue; Nijnik et al., 2018).
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691 Importantly that market-oriented social innovation studies have gaps in key aspects, largely in
692 the consideration of relationships between innovation and society. These aspects include: i) the
693 role that society and specific networks play in the development of innovations; and ii) how far
694 social innovations contribute to unlocking the potential growth and enhanced sustainable
695 development of society. Pertaining to forest-dependent communities, which use a substantial
696 proportion of resources obtained from forests for their own consumption (Sarkki et al., This
697 Issue), a key issue is the processing of forest goods and services prior to selling them through
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711 markets, and the roles that social innovation can play in this aspect of the value chain
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713 (Melnykovich et al., 2018).
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717 Also, when tackling the financing of social innovation, several different types of factors require
718 to be addressed. Those include availability of finance, finance regulations, and the culture,
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720 knowledge and attitudes of knowledge brokers and entrepreneurs as well as local people
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722 (Nijnik et al., 2017; Soe and Youn, This Issue). More effective approaches to financing also
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724 require the development and implementation of innovative models, e.g. public-private
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726 partnerships, new businesses and new markets, such as of non-wood forest products
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728 (Melnykovich et al., 2018), and building of stronger networks of intermediaries to play a
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730 decisive role in promoting social innovations.
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737 The different stages of social innovation entail different approaches to funding. At the outset,
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739 investment in prototypes and pilots is required to get ideas off the ground. Sources identified
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741 have covered a broad range of types, including public money through government and its
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743 agencies, charities, community and voluntary organizations, and foundations, and encouraging
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745 business engagement and the mobilizing of private funds.
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750 The evidence in the papers in This Issue explains the types of support required by the initiators
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752 and implementors of social innovations for them to develop their institutional and human
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754 capacities, including of becoming investment ready. Contributors to the Issue address market-
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756 oriented, forestry-based social innovations that offer new products or services and can function
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758 as social enterprises, mobilizing resources which can be unlocked within a regulatory
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760 framework of social entrepreneurship (Rogelja et al., 2018, This Issue). They also study the
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762 topic of co-operation and networking initiatives that are not market-oriented.
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773 Soe and Youn (2018, This Issue) describe the high level of dependency of communities in
774 Myanmar on non-marketed public goods from local forest resources. They identify and explain
775 the perceptions of forest-dependent communities in Myanmar towards participation in forest
776 conservation. Their results show that socially innovative engagement of forest-dependent
777 communities in nature conservation has a higher rate of success, if the community-based forest
778 conservation programme provides alternative opportunities for income, and if or when the
779 government can provide local people with access to land for agricultural production.
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790 Khadka et al. (2018, This Issue) present a Community based adaptation plan of action that
791 ensures a bottom-up planning process to minimize climate impacts on the livelihood of
792 vulnerable people and suggest adaptation actions for increasing resilience capacity in Nepal.
793 They recognize that it is difficult to generalize individual case study results within the diverse
794 geographical contexts of that country. However, they highlight that, in the context of Nepal, a
795 bottom-up, innovative, participatory process of community-based planning is likely to be the
796 most effective means of increasing community resilience.
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807 **4. Discussion**

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809 Forests contribute to the social, cultural and ecological dimensions of people's lives, and in
810 many areas around the world they are the cornerstone to their economic well-being through
811 employment and income for the local populations. However, there are trade-offs associated
812 with multiple forest ecosystem services that require study to identify the win-win solutions,
813 wherever they exist. In an empirical example of forest-dependent First Nations communities in
814 Canada, van Kooten et al. (2018) examine the trade-offs (and potential synergies) between
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829 revenue, as measured by net present value, employment, and carbon management (as a proxy
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831 for the ecological health of the forest) in forest ecosystems.
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836 Given the knowledge of trade-offs, the authors argue that there are management options that
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838 can improve upon current employment, wealth and/or ecological health of the forest. However,
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840 they conclude that none of the management strategies considered can satisfy all the technical,
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842 environmental and social/ cultural constraints whilst, at the same time, offer forest-based
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844 economic development that will prevent the decline of rural communities. Thus, to make a
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846 difference to forest-dependent First Nations communities, the proper integration of scientific
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848 and traditional knowledge and the enhancement of social innovation need to be promoted
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850 further, and in addition to markets and public support. Social innovation is a product of policy
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852 discourse that has led to the promotion of civic values as a means of delivering support and
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854 providing services, especially in places where markets and existing institutions fail.
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859 The European Union LEADER Programme has promoted bottom-up, local partnership-based
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861 development in disadvantaged regions. This model has been widely applied, creating
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863 opportunities for social innovations to emerge and to develop (Ludvig et al., 2018, This Issue).
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865 In Europe, social innovations are a key part of developing multi-national policy, such as the
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867 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), as well as national and regional policies and strategies.
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869 Ninety percent of European Union funding for forests is from the European Agricultural Fund
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871 for Rural Development (EAFRD), under the CAP. However, in several papers in This Issue, a
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873 deficit in the implementation of social innovation in relation to forestry is noted both, within
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875 the EU and beyond European boundaries.
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889 To use social innovation as a means of developing marginalized rural areas, it is essential to
890 consider local conditions and various intermediating factors (Secco et al., 2018, This Issue).
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892 Examples from Asia reflect common issues in relation to social innovation and forest-
893 dependent communities, in particularly important local contexts (Soe and Youn, 2018, This
894 Issue; Khadka et al., 2018, This Issue). Although scholars have developed approaches for
895 measuring the characteristics of social innovation processes, much remains to be done to link
896 social innovation with desired policy outcomes, on the ground (Ludvig et al., 2018, This Issue).
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905 Within the European Union, the roles of policy instruments, incentives and various entities as
906 catalysts and/or constraints to enhanced territorial governance are reviewed and analyzed. A
907 focus is on policy frameworks (e.g. EU Structural Fund regulations for 2014-2020), and
908 innovative governance solutions (e.g. the “network contracts” and new Rural Development
909 measures for collaboration, Art. 35 of EU RDP 2014-2020). In particular, attention is paid to
910 “regional systems” as ways of systematically fostering social innovations (Ludvig et al., 2018,
911 This Issue). This contributes to the promotion of institutional capacity building of forest-
912 dependent communities. This also enhances the development of social capital (Pisani et al.,
913 2017), and the skills required for supporting the creation of successful social innovations
914 through the advancement of knowledge which is co-constructed with stakeholders
915 (Kluvankova et al., 2018, This Issue).
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931 The pathway of innovations through to systemic change begins with ideas, developing into
932 prototypes and pilots, stabilisation of the initiatives and potentially up-scaling and out-scaling
933 beyond the place and people of origin, and may eventually create systemic changes (Polman et
934 al., 2017). Social innovations are more widespread in practice than reported in the scientific
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947 literature, institutional records, or Rural Development Programmes. Many social innovations
948 remain invisible; they are often neither synthesised, nor systematised.²
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953 Drawing on evidence from the case studies presented in This Issue, the conceptualisation of
954 social innovation (Polman et al., 2017; Kluvankova et al., 2018, This Issue) has been advanced
955 with respect to what it is; how it evolves; how local knowledge and cultures can be integrated
956 into decision-making (Nijnik et al., 2018, This Issue; Sarkki et al., This Issue); and how forest
957 policy instruments for social innovation can be assessed (Ludvig et al., 2018a, This Issue). The
958 inclusion of local knowledge and cultures has been facilitated by an improved understanding
959 of the attitudes and perceptions prevailing in forest-dependent communities (Nijnik et al.,
960 2017); their adaptation to threats by the integration of forest ecosystem services into, for
961 example, climate change adaptation plans (Khadka et al., 2018, This Issue); and, consideration
962 of options for topic specific plans, such as green energy (see Soloviy et al., This Issue) or nature
963 conservation (Soe and Youn, 2018, This Issue).
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979 We show that social innovation is a different concept from that of institutional innovation.
980 Social innovation occurs across the private, public and third sectors (SIMRA, 2016). Many
981 social innovations revolve around providing holistic, citizen-centred solutions which are likely
982 to cut across existing boundaries. Social innovations necessarily take place within specific
983 political structures (as well as social and economic) and rural policy frameworks, which can
984 enhance, enable, or/and create obstacles to opportunities for innovation (Kluvankova et al.,
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997 ² SIMRA has collated, analysed and categorised the catalogue of cases of social innovation, currently consisting
998 of approximately 380 examples, many of which are forest-based (Valero et al., 2017; Bryce et al., 2017).
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1006 2017). Policy and institutional support, along with strong civil society engagement, are usually
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1008 needed to drive social innovations (Bock, 2016; Ludvig et al., 2017).
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1013 Social innovations and associated new mechanisms of governance can be introduced by
1014 reforms of rural policy and/or institutional changes, entrepreneurs, or civic initiatives.
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1016 However, whatever the origin, nature and context of social innovations, they are characterized
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1018 by the relational processes that lead to a reconfiguration of social arrangements, networks and
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1020 institutional relations and values (SIMRA, 2016). These reconfigurations strengthen the ability
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1022 of actors to respond to societal challenges, and the beneficial development outcomes that might
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1024 arise (Polman et al., 2017). Thus, although social innovations may be associated with reforms
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1026 of rural policy, and may include the creation of new institutions, networks and governance
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1028 arrangements, they necessarily rely on the voluntary engagement of civil society actors
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1030 (Kluvankova et al., 2017). The outcomes of social innovation can be social, economic or
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1032 environmental, but social innovation is social in its means (Slee et al., 2018; Bock, 2016).
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1038 In line with Moulaert and Sekia (2003) and Papadopoulou et al. (2011), findings in This Issues
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1040 imply that innovations in forest-dependent communities depend on complex interactions, with
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1042 new aspects tackled under the umbrella of social innovation, including social processes
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1044 (Mulgan et al., 2007; Kluvankova et al., 2018, This Issue) and social impacts of innovation and
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1046 how these should be assessed (Secco et al., 2018, This Issue). The papers present theoretical
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1048 foundations, new empirical evidence, and analysis of social innovation, explaining how it
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1050 entails new practices, which target new products, services, models, social relationships and
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1052 collaborations. New fields of activity are also described, such as social entrepreneurship, social
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1054 enterprises, and nature-based businesses based on multi-sectoral interactions and citizen
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1056 involvement.
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5. Conclusions

The papers published in this Special Issue show that in marginalised rural areas³, where people depend on forests, social innovation has significant potential to deliver value and benefit for both local communities and forest ecosystems. The papers offer insights to policy instruments, incentives and policy mechanisms as catalysts for (or constraints to) the enhancement of territorial governance (Nijnik et al., 2018). They provide evidence of the key elements that should characterize an innovative approach to the evaluation of social innovations and their impacts (Secco et al., 2018, This Issue). These include the building of institutional capacity of forest-dependent communities, and the development of the social capital and skills required for supporting of their advance towards sustainability. The capacity building is through the co-construction of innovative knowledge with the overall goal of making a difference in marginalised rural areas.

We believe that social innovation can make a difference to the quality of life of people in forest-dependent communities. This belief is supported by empirical evidence presented in this Special Issue. Specifically, we demonstrate the role of social innovation for enabling policies and decision-making processes for the sustainable and multi-functional use of forests, and the promotion of traditional management of natural assets by local people. The evidence in the set of papers shows how the development of capabilities to tackle challenges faced by people living in remote rural areas will be helped by joint societal initiatives and innovative actions, together with the appropriate combination of top-down and bottom-up approaches to governance, supported by suitable policy instruments and incentives. Such joint societal initiatives involve scientific and practice communities, entrepreneurs, policy actors, investors and representatives of forest-dependent communities. This supports the achievement of the

³ For more information on the term marginalised rural areas and its explanation see Price et al., 2017.

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1124 primary objectives of social innovation of addressing concerns over the quality of life and the
1125 well-being of local people.
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1131 **Acknowledgement**

1132
1133 The authors are grateful to the European Commission for its support of the project on Social
1134 Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas (SIMRA, www.simra-h2020.eu) provided from the
1135 European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement
1136 No 677622 and the Scottish Government, who supported this research through their Rural
1137 Affairs and the Environment Strategic Research Programme. This Special Issue of Forest
1138 Policy and Economics is a follow-up of Thematic Session 197 organised by the SIMRA team
1139 at the 125th Anniversary Congress of the International Union of Forest Research Organizations
1140 (IUFRO, 2017, <http://iufro2017.com/>). We are grateful to colleagues in the SIMRA project for
1141 their comments on an earlier draft of this paper, and to the Editors of Forest Policy and
1142 Economics for helpful suggestions on the procedure.
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